

An Investigation on Butt-Joint Friction Stir Welding of Al7075-T6 to Al 7075-T6

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Abstract

Friction Stir Welding (FSW) is an advanced solid-state joining process. Junction is achieved by produced by the interaction between tool (pin and shoulder) and two parts by stirring materials the weld interfaces regions that generate the mechanical heat and very high plastic shear straining. Under such transient thermo-mechanical condition, materials to be FSWed can present the evolution in microstructures and resistances. The quality of the welding can be altered by the FSW parameters. The stability and repeatability of FSW is of major concern for industrial applications.

This contribution, deals with investigations on butt friction stir welding (FSW) of commercial Al 7075-T6 rolled plates. Four FSW trials are produced on 4 plates using the same welding parameters. From each plates five tensile specimens are cut by water jet for the evolution of the weld resistances and acceptance at room temperature. The very low measured surface roughness of the welds reveals a well controlled FSW mastering. RT tensile properties are repetitive with small and acceptable standard deviation. Tensile specimens are ruptured in TMAZ where the lower Vickers micro-hardness is found. The hardness profiles in the welds cross-sections present a “W” shape and present a drop in TMAZ and a maximum hardness in the BM.

Key words: friction stir welding, aluminum, tensile properties, hardness, microstructure

1. Introduction

Friction Stir Welding (FSW) is an advanced solid-state joining process invented in 1991 [1]. In this process, the weld is made by the combination of heating produced by friction between the tool and the work-piece and the stirring by the tool pin in the weld interface and the heat produced by mechanical plastic deformation.

In comparison to other welding techniques, FSW is a free-melting processing having the advantage of avoiding rapid melting/solidification phase transformations that can generate defects such as cracks and high internal strains/stresses (called residual stresses) that are usually encountered in general in welding of the high strength alloys such as 7XXX series aluminum alloys. This process can also be applied to dissimilar metals or even non-metallic materials such as polymers or ceramics.

During FSW, with the increasing of temperature, the thermally activated phenomena induce dynamic heat treatments that in coupling with mechanically induced shear plastic straining lead to significant evolutions in microstructural features for example the dynamic recrystallization. These evolutions affect the mechanical properties of welds. During recent years, although many investigations led to more comprehension of the pre-cited phenomena, the reduction of mechanical properties compared to the base material is often prohibitive for many applications.

1.1. Friction stir welding parameters

FSW parameters can be classified in 3 groups: process related, tool and environment parameters. Process parameters strongly depend on the equipment used and have been widely investigated in recent years [2-7]. Investigations on tool parameters [4-9] have shown that scrolls and threads enhance the material deformation and increase the weld quality and mechanical load bearing sustainability and resistance. It is also reported that conical pins are more adequate than cylindrical pins for a better defect-free welding. Parameters such as temperature, environment gas and the backing plates may affect the heat transfer in the weld materials and corrosion resistance [10]. Although FSW parameters are widely investigated, some trials are often run for the calibration and selecting/adjustment of the processing parameters prior launching the welding campaigns since some technical problems like clamping and excessive distortion of plates are difficult to master.

1.2. Mechanical properties

Tensile strength of Al-alloys strengthened by precipitation FSWed, is in general altered when they are tested in as-welded conditions. They are usually lower than of base Al-alloys along with both transverse and/or longitudinal directions of welding line. A very plausible reason is that the strengthening precipitates are at least partially dynamically dissolved in nugget area [11]. The post-welding heat treatments can become therefore mandatory for increasing the mechanical resistance by generating the new precipitation or even coalesce. Such heat treatments enhance the over-all welds' strength but at the same time they reduce in general the ductility of FSW components [12]. However, it is difficult to reach the strength of the base material. In many locations along the weld line, the profile of hardness crossing perpendicular to the weld line presents a 'W' shape evolution of Al alloys. Usually the hardness is low in the Heat Affected Zone (HAZ) and it is medium in the weld nugget. A relevant ageing heat treatment can enhance the resistance and hardness in the weld nugget [13].

1.3. Microstructural features

One of the advantages of FSW is to produce fine microstructure in the weld nugget. That microstructure is the result of dynamic recrystallization as the nugget that experiences the high shear plastic strain stirring and generating consequently the mechanical heat that increase the temperature [11]. The friction between tool and plates contributes naturally very much in increasing the temperature as well. It is commonly observed that the finest grains are obtained from 'cold welds' while 'hot welds' lead to less fine grains. As a consequence of the dynamic recrystallization, the nugget's microstructure has a large fraction of high angle boundaries (HAB) and a low density of dislocations [14]. However, some nugget grains can contain high dislocation density. As explained by Jata et al. [13], this may be due to post-recrystallization straining. In the Thermo-Mechanically Affected Zone (TMAZ), grains are usually coarsen and elongated while no difference is observed between the HAZ and the base metal concerning grains' size and aspect [11, 15]. Evolution of precipitates is highly related to the peak temperatures reached during FSW, which depend obviously on the welding parameters and conditions. For extremely 'hot welds', the non-strengthening phase forms and makes the weld non-responsive to post-heat treatments [16]. For classic hot welds, it is mostly observed a complete dissolution of precipitates and after post-weld heat treatments strengthening phases as GP zones, η and η' form [11].

This contribution deals with an investigation on surface roughness and mechanical properties of Al-7075 T6 similar plates butt joint by FSW. The surface characteristics and tensile properties of welded plates are reported for a prescribed welding condition. The repeatability of the process and the microstructural features are reported.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1. Material and welding conditions

Commercial Al 7075-T6 rolled plates are cut by water jet to obtain 8 plates of equal size (2 mm thick, 300 mm long and 100 mm wide). The chemical composition of this alloy is reported in table 1. The welds are produced at AVANTIS Project center on a robot equipped FSW head. Several calibration tests are run to set the suitable parameters leading to defect-free welding. The FSW tool used consists of a stainless-steel material with conical and threaded pin and scrolled shoulder. The welding samples are clamped over a stainless-steel backing plate. Four butt joint welds are produced with similar welding parameters, in order to investigate the repeatability of the process.

Tableau 1 : Chemical composition of the 7075-T6-aluminum alloy (in mass %).

Cu	Mg	Zn	Cr	Fe	Si	Mn	Ti	Al
1.52	2.63	5.59	0.24	0.21	0.07	0.06	0.02	Balanced

2.2. Characterization of welds

From each weld trial, five tensile test specimens are machined by water jet cutting as shown on Figure 1. First, surface roughness is evaluated to investigate the influence of the welding on the surface finish. An Altisurf 520 (ALTIMET France) equipped by an extended confocal field microscopy and chromatic optical probe with 350 μ m field depth, is employed. An area of 11 mm \times 6 mm, Figure 2, is evaluated with the step-wises of 100 μ m in Y-direction and 1 μ m in X-direction.

Figure 1 : Positions of tensile specimens cut from butt-welds.

The tensile tests are carried out at room temperature on plate specimens by a mechanical Zwick machine until complete failure in quasi-static condition with a crosshead rate of 0.5mm/min. The displacement in the gage length is measured with an attached extensometer. The samples next to each tensile specimen are taken for microstructural investigations and hardness measurements (see as example the sample of specimen 1 is section AA of Figure 1). The micro-hardness is measured (100g loading, 10s) using a Buehler machine. Macroscopic microstructural observations are made by a Keyence microscope. The samples are first polished by an adequate metallographic procedure and etched with Keller's reagent for optical and/or SEM investigations.

Figure 2 : A typical area of roughness measurement.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Surface roughness

A typical 3D evaluation of the surface topology is reported in Figure 3. The roughness of the surface for all specimens is presented by the parameter S_a in Table 2. S_a is an arithmetic mean in absolute value of the difference in height of each point with respect to the average of surface plan. It is the extension of the parameter R_a (arithmetic mean height along a line) to a surface and is expressed as:

$$S_a = \frac{1}{A} \iint_A |z(x, y)| dx dy \quad (1)$$

where A is the surface area and $z(x, y)$ is the difference in height between the measured point and the average plane of the surface.

Figure 3 : Typical surface roughness measurement in: (A) top view, (B): isometric view.

Table 2 : Sa parameter of FSW and BM specimens in different plates.

Specimen		Sa (μm)			
		Plate 1	Plate 2	Plate 3	Plate 4
1		17.0	18.1	17.3	18.4
2		18.1	18.2	21.1	19.7
3		17.2	16.8	18.7	17.7
4		18.1	17.9	19.9	26.8
5		18.2	17.2	20.4	20.1
Per Plate	Minimum	17.0	16.8	17.3	17.7
	Maximum	18.2	18.2	21.1	26.8
	Mean	17.7	17.6	19.5	20.5
	Standard Deviation	0.57	0.61	1.50	3.63
	<i>Base material</i>	<i>1.2</i>	<i>1.2</i>	<i>1.2</i>	<i>1.2</i>

The surface roughness of FSW parts is highly sensitive to the presence of defects, especially high flash, the can increase drastically the “mean” roughness. The mean Sa in each FSW trials per plate is relatively low, proving a well uniform and stable welding process mastering. As a comparison to advanced Additive Layer Manufacturing (ALM) where one/multi-layer are “joined” by liquid type welding, the Sa values achieved in present investigation are slightly lower (see as an example the

Sa=21 μ m of Ti-6Al-4V SLM [17]). Furthermore, many post-processing techniques such as sandblasting or vibro finishing can lower the overall roughness of FSW parts.

3.2. Microstructure

Figure 4 shows the cross-section macrograph of FSW specimen 1 from plate 1. The grain size and grain shape reveals four microstructure zones with different metallurgical features. The detailed of the nugget zone feature is presented on Figure 5 at different magnifications. As can be observed there is no tunnel or penetration of the tool material into nugget region. The nugget is an ultrafine grain (UFG) microstructure that is difficultly visible very clearly on optical microscopy (Figure 5b). Such UFG microstructure is the consequence of dynamic recrystallization of the initial material grains experiencing the concomitant and coupling actions of the huge shear plastic straining and temperature increase-up during FSW processing. It is known UFG enhances the ductility and the mechanical strength. In the absence of the direct tensile testing of “meso-specimens” extracted from different regions, the micro-hardness measurements can indicate via well-recognized Hall-Patch empirical relationship a first and acceptable approximation of the “local tensile” behavior and properties such as Yield stress and UTS in these 4 specific regions (nugget, TMAZ, HAZ, BM) in FSW [18]. It should be highlighted that the microstructural evolutions are due to different specific thermo-mechanical loading histories at each region. The maximum temperature and amplitude of strain/stress are different and therefore temperature and strain rate dependent softening phenomena are different. Therefore, the room temperature hardness is only a qualitative indication of a specific and complex high temperature transient thermo-mechanical loading that is associated and coupled with the material microstructural evolutions.

Figure 4 : Optical macrograph of the cross-section of specimen 1 showing different metallurgical zones.

Figure 6 shows detailed of microstructures in base material (BM) and TMAZ. Slightly coarser and deformed grains than in BM characterize the TMAZ's microstructure. The presence of such deformed grains confirms mechanical energy stored locally at high temperatures by the accumulation of shear strain increments is presumably not high enough to achieve a critical level leading to reduce by dynamic recrystallization the density of accumulated and entangled dislocations by self-organization via climbing/cross-slipping of dislocations, self-healing and/or displacement of grain boundaries as plan defects and grain rotation.

Figure 5 : optical micrographs showing microstructure in the weld nugget at different scales.

Figure 6 : Optical micrographs of specimen 1 of plate 1 showing microstructure in (a): TMAZ and (b) base material

3.3. Tensile properties

The Figure 8 shows as an example the evolution of tensile curves of the nominal (engineering) stress versus the nominal strain for all specimens (FSW and BM) of plate 1. All FSW tensile specimens exhibit similar trends and characteristics, namely, the elastic-plastic behavior and non-linear strain work hardening, the yield stress and UTS with rather small variations in rupture ductility. As Young's modulus is known to be a "physical property" depending upon the lattice cell structure and bond forces both FSW and BM present very close Young's modulus. The tensile elastic-plastic behavior of BM is different. BM presents the higher yield stress and UTS in comparison to FSW and has a lower and a relative constant strain work-hardening exponent. The higher yield stress and UTS of BM is related to the state of its initial microstructure that governs the plastic deformation and also the strain work hardening by entanglement of mobile dislocations interacting with the precipitates or grain boundaries lowering so far the tensile rupture ductility. During FSW the initial elastically self-strained stored energy of BM microstructures, facilitates the thermo-mechanical softening by self-reorganization of dislocations reducing the internal energy and distortions and thus the over-all yield stress and inversely enhancing the strain rupture (ductility or rupture elongation). Dynamic recrystallization increases the strain work hardening of FSW regions. A convective yield stress ($YS_{0.2}$, corresponding to 0.2% plastic strain) and a non-convective yield stress (YS corresponding to nil plastic strain, called "real yield stress") are introduced in order to better reveal the early hardening of FSW specimens between these two stress levels (see Figure 7 and data collected in Table 3 -Table 6). The UTS of FSW could achieve the UTS of BM if the necking and plastic localization would not occur. Tensile specimens are broken in the TMAZ either in the advancing side or in the retreating side. It means that, the welded zone was subjected to a thermal and/or mechanical treatment that increases ductility. Tensile tests with image correlation are expected to identify these zones.

Figure 8 : stress – strain curves obtained from weld 1.

Table 3 : Tensile properties obtained from FSW trials in Plate 1.

Specimen	E (GPa)	YS (MPa)	Y0.2 (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	
1	65.71	319.99	365.79	514.83	10.08	
2	66.43	339.33	375.45	513.96	8.45	
3	71.43	343.41	393.53	536.48	9.59	
4	68.67	333.44	388.189	511.91	6.71	
5	72.62	331.9	382.58	528.76	10.05	
Plate 1	Maximum	72.62	343.41	393.53	536.48	10.08
	Minimum	65.71	319.99	365.79	511.91	7.97
	Mean	68.97	333.61	381.11	521.19	9.41
	Standard Deviation	3.02	8.9	10.88	10.84	0.86
	Base material	76.76	414.14	493.09	565.65	8.00

Table 4 : Tensile properties obtained from FSW trials in Plate 2.

Specimen	E (GPa)	YS (MPa)	Y0.2 (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	
1	69.90	312.74	385.98	532.43	10.29	
2	70.70	348.03	398.23	542.25	11.21	
3	74.15	338.36	401.69	510.70	4.71	
4	69.69	366.62	398.29	544.83	11.20	
5	68.021	331.98	395.93	533.75	8.63	
Plate 2	Maximum	74.15	366.62	401.69	544.83	11.21
	Minimum	68.02	312.74	385.98	510.70	4.71
	Mean	70.50	339.54	396.02	532.79	9.21
	Standard Deviation	22.65	19.89	5.98	13.45	2.73
	Base material	72.77	441.50	497.89	567.84	7.10

Table 5 : Tensile properties obtained from FSW trials in Plate 3.

Specimen	E (GPa)	YS (MPa)	Y0.2 (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	
1	70.61	332.38	380.29	534.83	10.64	
2	72.05	332.38	384.29	534.83	10.64	
3	75.66	360.01	388.56	538.33	7.57	
4	72.94	323.92	399.82	542.18	7.97	
5	74.24	313.43	385.25	529.40	8.03	
Plate 3	Maximum	75.66	360.01	399.82	542.18	10.64
	Minimum	70.61	313.43	380.29	529.40	7.57
	Mean	72.81	332.42	386.84	535.92	8.97
	Standard Deviation	2,23	17.28	8.05	4.74	1.53
	Base material	72.45	445.73	498.14	567.63	6.57

Table 6 : Tensile properties obtained in FSW trial in Plate 4.

Specimen	E (GPa)	YS (MPa)	Y0.2 (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	El. (%)	
1	71.80	326.01	379.19	522.72	8.14	
2	71.82	324.28	386.20	535.28	10.12	
3	73.13	345.68	395.63	539.09	8.69	
4	71.65	306.84	388.19	516.61	6.63	
5	72.41	313.40	387.25	524.40	7.03	
Plate 4	Maximum	73.13	345.68	395.63	539.09	10.12
	Minimum	71.65	306.84	379.19	516.61	6.63
	Mean	72.16	323.24	387.29	527.62	8.12
	Standard Deviation	0.62	14.82	5.86	9.30	1.39
	Base material	75.42	447.35	501.00	571.79	7.31

As can be observed, there is certain uniformity in the tensile properties of the specimen of different FSW trials. Specimen 3 of Plat 3 exhibits the minimum tensile strength (510.87 MPa) that is 90% joint efficiency. This value is close or greater than of the most of results reported for as-weld joint efficiency for the same alloy. The joint efficiency reported by Vargas et al. [19] is up to 89% while İpekoğlu et al. [20] mentioned 79% efficiency. The highest tensile strength is 544.83 MPa, with joint efficiency of about 96%.

3.4. Vickers hardness

As an example Vickers Micro-hardness map of specimen 1 from the first FSW Plate is presented on Figure 9. From the outer to the center of the weld, the hardness is first high and then drops slowly to reach the minimum and finally increases slightly again. The hardness drops in HAZ and TMAZ regions and increases slightly in the weld nugget. Thanks to the macrograph of the weld section (Figure 4), on can conclude that the maximum hardness is located in BM.

Figure 9 : Vickers Hardness map of specimen 1 of weld 1.

For the other samples, Vickers micro-hardness are measured at mid-thickness in the welds' cross-section. As an example, Figure 10 presents hardness profiles for the specimens of weld 1. All these specimens have the 'W' shape usually observed in aluminum alloys. Table 7 Table 10 present as an example the evolution of micro-hardness measured along the cross-sections of all specimens extracted from the Plate 1 between BM and nugget region in advancing sides (AS) and the retreating sides (RS). For each specimen, hardness in the weld nugget is the mean hardness of the 5 central points of the profile. Hardness in the TMAZ is given by the mean of the three minimum hardness values. It can be observed that hardness is relatively stable independently to the weld or specimen. Also, there is no significant difference between the advancing sides and the retreating sides of the welds. The weakest zone is located at TMAZ. This explains why the failure during tensile tests occurred in these zones. Aluminum 7075-T6 is a strengthened alloy by the precipitating hardening mechanisms. During the FSW processing, the higher temperature is achieved, the more quantity of precipitates is dissolved. Regarding the hardness profiles, one can conclude that the overall drop of hardness in specific zones of welds (HAZ + TMAZ + nugget) is due to dissolution of precipitates. The zones closer to the weld centerline are more heated-up and by consequence more precipitates are dissolved lowering the local hardness. The local post-FSW heat-treatments might refurbish and thus the overall strength of weld parts enhance by appropriate re-precipitation and ageing. It should however be emphasized that precipitation sole would not explain the hardness profile evolution and other microstructural features like grain size in particular and/or dislocation density (mobile and forest) can additionally influence such hardness evolution.

Figure 10 : Vickers hardness profiles at mid-center in the welds' sections of specimens of weld 1.

Table 7 : Micro-hardness in nugget and TMAZ of specimens extracted from welds in Plate 1.

Specimen		Hv (100g)		
		Nugget	TMAZ - RS	TMAZ-AS
	1	136.20	124.00	122.33
	2	138.00	125.33	119.67
	3	139.00	125.67	123.00
	4	139.20	119.33	120.67
	5	139.80	119.33	120.00
Plate 1	Maximum	139.80	125.67	123.00
	Minimum	136.20	119.33	119.67
	Mean	138.44	122.73	121.13
	Standard Deviation	1.41	3.17	1.46

Table 8 : Micro-hardness in nugget and TMAZ of specimens extracted from welds in Plate 2.

Specimen		Hv (100g)		
		Nugget	TMAZ - RS	TMAZ-AS
	1	141.00	121.00	123.00
	2	133.80	116.33	122.33
	3	136.60	118.00	121.33
	4	142.40	124.33	122.67
	5	134.60	113.00	117.33
Plate 2	Maximum	142.40	124.33	123.00
	Minimum	133.80	113.00	117.33
	Mean	137.68	118.53	121.33
	Standard Deviation	3.84	4.34	2.32

Table 9 : Micro-hardness in nugget and TMAZ of specimens extracted from welds in Plate 3.

Specimen		Hv (100g)		
		Nugget	TMAZ - RS	TMAZ-AS
1		136.40	119.67	111.33
2		130.40	115.33	113.00
3		134.80	119.00	119.67
4		141.40	126.33	123.67
5		142.20	124.33	123.33
Plate 3	Maximum	142.20	126.33	123.67
	Minimum	130.40	115.33	111.33
	Mean	137.04	120.93	118.20
	Standard Deviation	4.88	4.40	5.76

Table 10 : Micro-hardness in nugget and TMAZ of specimens extracted from welds in Plate 4.

Specimen		Hv (100g)		
		Nugget	TMAZ - RS	TMAZ-AS
1		144.60	124.33	123.33
2		133.60	110.33	117.67
3		134.80	109.33	116.67
4		130.20	112.67	110.67
5		133.20	109.33	112.67
Plate 4	Maximum	144.60	124.33	123.33
	Minimum	130.20	109.33	110.67
	Mean	135.28	113.20	116.20
	Standard Deviation	5.48	6.37	4.91

For example, if one considers that precipitate features (size, distribution), dislocation density and precipitate-dislocation interactions influence solely the hardness, its profile would decrease gradually from the BM to the weld centerline and present a plateau in the nugget (Figure 11a). Such hardness evolution could be observed if the grain size remains uniform regardless the position in the weld. In this case, hardness could be controlled as a function φ .

$$HV = \varphi(p_1, \dots, p_i, \rho) \quad (2)$$

with p_i as characteristic parameter depending on precipitate i and dislocation density ρ contributions.

If one considers that hardness is only influenced by grain size, then hardness evolution can be expressed by a function ϕ that could for example be Hall-Petch law as:

$$Hv = \phi(d) \quad (3)$$

with d as the grain size. Compared to the BM, the hardness would decrease in TMAZ and then increase until achieving the hardness in the weld nugget that has the smallest grain size (e.g. UFG) (Figure 11b). This type of profile is often observed on welds made on non-precipitate strengthening alloys like Ti-6Al-4V [7].

Figure 11 : Hardness profile considering (a) influence of precipitates only and (b) influence of grain size only.

In most cases the real hardness evolution is in-between of these two cases and the grain size and precipitate/dislocations features contribute simultaneously on the local hardness and mechanical properties and evolution profiles.

4. Conclusions

This contribution, deals with investigations on butt friction stir welding (FSW) of a 7075-T6-aluminum alloy. Four FSW trials are produced on 4 plates using the same welding parameters.

It is shown that:

- The welds present a very good macroscopic aspect and the surface roughness parameter is very low.
- RT tensile properties are repetitive.
- The tensile strength is very high with a joint efficiency between 90% and 96%.
- The tensile specimens are ruptured in TMAZ where the Vickers hardness is lower.
- The hardness profiles in the welds have a “W” shape and present a drop in TMAZ and a maximum hardness in the BM.
- The microstructure is very fine grains in the weld nugget and coarse grains in the TMAZ

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